

PRIORITY SKILLS FOR THE LATVIAN LABOUR MARKET: RESULTS OF A STAKEHOLDER SURVEY*Skorobogatova O.**Mg.oec., Lecturer of the Faculty of Transport and Management
Transport and Telecommunication Institute, Latvia***Abstract**

The stakeholder survey allows to identify which skills are in demand in the Latvian labor market and to assess the extent to which training meets the requirements of employers. The results obtained can be used to optimize training strategies and increase the competitiveness of employees, which in turn contributes to improving the overall efficiency of the labor market. In the context of population ageing, migration and technological change, the study of skills in demand is an important step for creating a balanced and efficient labor market in Latvia. This makes this study relevant for all stakeholders - from state structures and educational institutions to employers and employees.

Keywords: skills, Latvia, labour market, stakeholder survey, recommendations.

Introduction

The relevance of the study is due to rapid changes in the Latvian labour market caused by globalization, digitalization and technological innovations. Modern economic and social conditions require new competencies and flexibility from employees to adapt to changing market needs. At the same time, both technical and interpersonal skills such as critical thinking, communication and learning ability are becoming key success factors.

The aim of this study is to identify priority professional skills in demand in the Latvian labor market. The study aims to understand the key competencies that are necessary to improve the competitiveness of employees and to effectively adapt to changes in the labor market caused by technological, social and economic transformations. The results obtained can be used to optimize educational programs, as well as to develop skills development strategies, which contributes to improving the overall efficiency of the labor market and reducing the gap between employers' expectations and the level of applicants' training.

As outlined in the McKinsey Global Institute's report (2024): physical skills are still important, but technological, social and emotional skills may be more in demand. [3] The focus is shifting from traditional skills and narrow specialization to broader and more comprehensive competencies that include the ability to adapt to a rapidly changing environment, learn new technologies and use digital tools effectively.

Latvia, one of the countries in the Baltic region, has gone through significant changes in its economy and employment structure since regaining independence in 1991. The transformations associated with the shift from a centrally planned economy to a market economy, as well as the impact of global economic trends, have had a significant impact on the country's labor market.

At the beginning of 2024, Latvia had a population of 1 million 872 thousand. 11.1 thousand less than a

year earlier, according to data from the Central Statistical Office. [2] In 2023, 945.7 thousand people were economically active in Latvia, which is slightly more than two thirds or 68.6% of the total population aged 15-74. [1]

Research Methodology

In order to analyze the priority skills in demand in the Latvian labour market, a methodology was applied, including the use of hierarchical clustering to identify key groups of skills relevant for different sectors of the economy. At the first stage of the study, data reflecting employers' requirements to candidates was collected, which allowed to form a complete picture of the competencies in demand. Vacancies, corporate documents and analytical reports of the companies were used as input data, which ensured the comprehensiveness of the approach.

To systematize and analyze the information obtained, content analysis was used to identify and classify the key requirements outlined by employers. This method facilitated the identification of 126 unique skills, which were subsequently categorized using cluster analysis. The classification of skills into 38 categories was done based on their structural and functional similarities, which provided a deeper understanding of the composition of the competencies in demand in the Latvian labor market.

All companies participating in the study have international experience, have significant business expertise and manage large teams of employees. This makes their skill requirements and perceptions relevant to a wide range of professional fields and markets.

The usage of statistical analysis made it possible to identify the most significant skill clusters by calculating their frequency among the surveyed companies. As a result of the analysis, 21 skill clusters were identified (Table 1), which were the most frequently encountered and represented the key competencies demanded by modern organizations.

Table 1

Key skills clusters (created by the author, 2024)

Nr.	Skills cluster	Skills
1	Accountability	Responsibility for decisions; Taking accountability for mistakes; A responsible approach to work
2	Adaptability	Adjusting to changes; Flexible approaches; Managing stressful situations; Emotional resilience
3	Client Orientation	Focus on client needs; Maintaining client relationships; Creating value for clients
4	Commercial Awareness	Understanding business processes; Financial literacy; Risk and opportunity assessment; Market awareness; Identifying new opportunities
5	Commitment to Continuous Learning	Continuous professional development; Self-education; Willingness to learn new things; Organizing employee training
6	Communication	Persuasion skills; Effective business communication; Building trust-based relationships
7	Creating New Value	Generating new opportunities; Implementing innovations; Developing partnerships; Creating new value
8	Creativity	Developing new ideas; Generating unconventional solutions; Seeking new approaches; Innovative thinking
9	Influential	Inspiring through personal example and behavior; Personal authority; Mentoring skills; Setting long-term goals
10	Integrity Focused	High ethical standards; Building team trust; Personal honesty; Adherence to ethics and norms
11	Leadership, Trustworthiness & Ethics	Leadership qualities; Team management; Ability to make complex decisions; Building trust within the team; Delegating authority
12	Organizational Skills	Developing structures and systems; Attention to detail; Creating regulations and procedures; Project management; Multitasking
13	Planning and Organization	Task and deadline planning; Priority management; Resource allocation; Effective workflow organization
14	Positive Outlook	Maintaining a positive attitude; Motivating others; Identifying opportunities in challenging situations
15	Problem Solving	Creative problem solving; Effective decision-making; Critical analysis; Comprehensive solutions
16	Reconciling Tensions and Dilemmas	Conflict resolution; Managing dilemmas; Balancing interests; Resolving complex situations
17	Responsibility	Responsibility for tasks; Balancing interests; Time management
18	Strategic Networking	Building professional connections; Maintaining a good business reputation; Negotiation skills; Managing business contacts; Cross-cultural collaboration
19	Teamwork	Working in cross-functional teams; Division of responsibilities; Team engagement in processes; Building partnerships
20	Technological Awareness	Proficiency in modern technologies; Digital data analysis; Mastering new technical tools; Digital literacy; Process automation; Ensuring information security
21	Vision Sharing	Envisioning a common future; Sharing knowledge

The results confirmed that employers from leading countries focus on a limited set of key skills, which reflects the current changes in the labor market caused by the processes of digitalization, globalization and transformation of business models. These findings underscore the importance of these competencies in the context of organizations' adaptation to new economic and technological challenges.

Results of the Study

As part of the research, three questionnaires were developed targeting three key groups of Latvian labor market participants: representatives of employers holding top management positions in companies, specialists of recruitment agencies and students. The purpose of the surveys was to investigate the perception and evaluation of the importance of 21 skill groups. Participants were asked to rate each skill group on a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (extremely important), which

allowed to identify the priorities of each group in the context of their professional and educational expectations.

To analyze the obtained data, the cluster analysis technique was used, aimed at identifying groups of skills characterized by similar average values of assessments. This approach allowed to identify the most prioritized skills, as well as to determine those of the presented skills that are perceived as less important. In order to ensure systematic and objective interpretation of the data, all skills were classified into four clusters:

1. Skills with the highest mean scores (range: 3.68 - 5.00)
2. Skills with high average scores (range: 3.45 - 3.67)
3. Skills with moderate but below average scores (range: 2.84 - 3.44)

4. Skills with the lowest average scores (range: 0 - 2.83)

The presented classification allows to reflect the level of importance of each group of skills and provides a differentiated approach to the analysis of their perception in the context of professional expectations of labor market participants.

At the first stage of the research, the author conducted 18 interviews with representatives of top management. In the process of preparing this stage, specific

criteria for selecting respondents were established. The main criterion for inclusion was at least 10 years of work experience in managerial positions, which ensured a high level of professional competence and depth of knowledge of the participants in the context of the topic under consideration.

Figure 1 presents the five most important professional skills that top managers rated as Extremely Important, with the percentage of respondents who gave each of them the highest rating.

Figure 1. Top 5 most in-demand skills as assessed by top managers (created by the author, 2024)

Influence is one of the key factors contributing to the success of both individual employees and the team as a whole. In a dynamically changing business environment, the ability to influence allows an employee not only to perform assigned tasks, but also to actively participate in processes, making a meaningful contribution to the development of the organization. Top managers highly value this skill, as it is directly related to successful implementation of changes, solving complex problems and achieving strategic business goals.

At the second stage of the study, the author collected responses from representatives of recruitment agencies operating in Latvia. Forty-seven respondents representing 21 agencies took part in the survey. The criterion for the selection of agencies was high assessment of their clients, which ensured the participation of

organizations with a proven reputation and high quality of services provided.

In order to improve the accuracy of the results, the survey was conducted among professionals at various levels within the agencies, including recruiters, account managers and supervisors. This approach allowed to collect the opinions of representatives with different levels of responsibility and professional experience, which contributed to a more comprehensive assessment of the aspects under consideration.

Figure 2 illustrates the five most important skills that recruiters rated as Extremely Important. The X-axis shows the percentage of respondents who assigned a given level of importance to each skill.

Figure 2. Top 5 most in-demand skills as assessed by employees of recruiting agencies (created by the author, 2024)

The highest priority was given to skills that promote effective teamwork and quick adaptation to change, which is especially important in a rapidly advancing technological environment.

At the third stage of the study, the author organized a survey of students of three Latvian higher education institutions. The study involved 327 students representing different levels of education and studying different specialties. Such a diverse composition of respondents allowed to collect a wider range of opinions regarding the importance of professional skills. Both senior students, many of whom are already active par-

ticipants in the labor market, and junior students preparing to enter the labor market participated in the survey. The survey was conducted using online questionnaires.

The general trend indicates that students emphasize skills that they believe will be useful to them immediately after graduation, while less attention is paid to managerial skills, whose importance increases later in their professional careers.

Figure 3 presents the five occupational skills that students who participated in the survey rated as Extremely Important.

Figure 3. Top 5 most in-demand skills as assessed by students (created by the author, 2024)

Despite the high importance of the mentioned practical skills, the students' emphasis is probably due to their current level of training and lack of experience in a professional environment.

Conclusion

The analysis allows the author to identify differences in the perception of the importance of professional skills between three key groups of respondents - top managers, employees of Latvian recruitment agencies and students. This contributes to understanding which skills are most important for each group, as well as identifying points of divergence in their assessments.

Table 2 shows the summary results of the conducted surveys. The results can serve as a basis for the

development of programs to improve the skills of employees, taking into account the priorities of top managers and recruiters. This will allow companies and educational institutions to develop those skills that are most in demand in today's labor market. Recruitment agencies can use this information to analyze discrepancies in the priorities of students and employers, which will help to formulate requirements for candidates more accurately and target those who meet employers' expectations. In addition, the identified results may help students to realize the differences between their perception of skills and real expectations of employers, which, in the author's opinion, will stimulate their attention to the development of underestimated, but in demand on the labor market skills.

Table 2

Ranking of 21 professional skills in terms of importance for top managers, employees of recruiting agencies and students who participated in the survey (created by the author, 2024)

	top managers	recruitment agencies	students
1	Influential	Teamwork	Problem Solving
2	Responsibility	Adaptability	Responsibility
3	Commitment to Continuous Learning	Technological Awareness	Creativity
4	Vision Sharing	Vision Sharing	Organizational Skills
5	Client Orientation	Responsibility	Communication Skills
6	Accountability	Commitment to Continuous Learning	Technological Awareness
7	Technological Awareness	Client Orientation	Adaptable
8	Communication Skills	Communication Skills	Planning and Organization
9	Problem Solving	Problem Solving	Leadership, Trustworthiness & Ethics
10	Adaptability	Positive Outlook	Reconciling tensions and dilemmas
11	Positive Outlook	Creativity	Strategic Networking
12	Organizational Skills	Organizational Skills	Commitment to Continuous Learning
13	Commercial Awareness	Reconciling Tensions and Dilemmas	Commercial Awareness
14	Leadership, Trustworthiness & Ethics	Commercial Awareness	Integrity Focused
15	Teamwork	Leadership, Trustworthiness & Ethics	Positive Outlook
16	Creativity	Planning and Organization	Client Orientation
17	Reconciling Tensions and Dilemmas	Strategic Networking	Accountability
18	Planning and Organization	Integrity Focused	Creating new value
19	Creating New Value	Creating New Value	Vision Sharing
20	Integrity Focused	Accountability	Teamwork
21	Strategic Networking	Influential	Influential

Assessing the results of the comparison, it is necessary to note the differences in the priorities of professional skills among the three groups of respondents. Top managers attach the greatest importance to leadership and strategic skills, such as the ability to influence and focus on client needs. Recruiters, on the other hand, emphasize collaboration and adaptability skills, including teamwork and flexibility. Students highlight skills related to problem solving, responsibility and creativity, reflecting their perception of the key requirements of today's labor market.

The author suggests that decision-makers need to focus educational efforts on strengthening the basic skills that students consider most important. At the same time, attention should be paid to developing students' awareness of the importance of long-term and strategic competencies in order to prepare them for the realities of today's labor market and ensure their competitiveness in the future.

References

1. Centrālā statistiskās pārvalde. Darbaspēka apsekojuma galvenie rādītāji 2023. gadā. Available at: https://admin.stat.gov.lv/system/files/publication/2024-05/Nr_09_Darbaspēka_apsekojuma_galvenie_raditaji_2023_gada_%2824_00%29_LV.pdf [Accessed: 07-02-2025]
2. Centrālā statistiskās pārvalde. Iedzīvotāju skaits un tā izmaiņas. <https://stat.gov.lv/lv/statistikas-temas/iedzivotaji/iedzivotaju-skaits/247-iedzivotaju-skaits-un-ta-izmainas?themeCode=IR> [Accessed: 07-02-2025]
3. Hazan, E., Madgavkar, A., Chui, M., etc., A new future of work: The race to deploy AI and raise skills in Europe and beyond. McKinsey Global Institute. https://www.mckinsey.de/~media/mckinsey/locations/europe%20and%20middle%20east/deutschland/news/presse/2024/2024%20-%202005%20-%202023%20mgi%20genai%20future%20of%20work/mgi%20report_a-new-future-of-work-the-race-to-deploy-ai.pdf [Accessed: 07-02-2025]